

SPECIFICS OF CREATING PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR SELF-MANAGEMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The article describes the possibility of creating pedagogical conditions for the inclusion of future teachers in the system of research activities. The theory and practice of implementing pedagogical conditions for the inclusion of future teachers in the system of scientific and pedagogical work is implemented through the technology of system pedagogical modeling (pedagogical technology for the formation of a culture of independent work). The paper clarifies the concept of "pedagogical conditions for the inclusion of future teachers in scientific research work", provides statistics of implemented ideas in the practice of training students of pedagogical specialties.*

Keywords: *pedagogical conditions, self-management, technology of systematic pedagogical modeling, culture of the individual's selfdependent work, scientific-pedagogical work.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada kelajakdagi o'qituvchilarni ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyati tizimiga kiritish uchun pedagogik shart-sharoitlarni yaratish imkoniyati tasvirlangan. Kelajakdagi o'qituvchilarni ilmiy-pedagogik ish tizimiga kiritish uchun pedagogik sharoitlarni amalga oshirish nazariyasi va amaliyoti tizimli pedagogik modellashtirish texnologiyasi (mustaqil ish madaniyatini shakllantirishning pedagogik texnologiyasi) orqali amalga oshiriladi. Asarda "bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlariga kiritishning pedagogik shartlari" tushunchasi, pedagogik mutaxassisliklar talabalarini tayyorlash amaliyotida amalga oshirilayotgan g'oyalar statistikasi ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pedagogik sharoitlar, o'zini o'zi boshqarish, tizim va pedagogik modellashtirish texnologiyasi, shaxsning mustaqil ish madaniyati, ilmiy va pedagogik ish.*

Аннотация. *В статье описана возможность создания педагогических условий включения будущих педагогов в систему научно-исследовательской деятельности. Теория и практика реализации педагогических условий включения будущих педагогов в систему научно-педагогической работы реализуется через технологию системнопедагогического моделирования (педагогическая технология формирования культуры самостоятельной работы). В работе уточнено понятие «педагогические условия включения будущих педагогов в научноисследовательскую работу», приведена статистика реализуемых идей в практике подготовки студентов педагогических специальностей.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогические условия, самоуправление, технология системно-педагогического моделирования, культура самостоятельной работы личности, научно-педагогическая работа.*

Modern education in the structure of training teachers treat the definition and solution of the problem of high-quality, timely development of the student's personality and optimal performance of professional and labor functions with careful attention, because the quality of professional and pedagogical education of the present time directly depends on the quality of continuing education of the future. It is impossible to underestimate the value of the productive formation of a teacher in the implemented model of professional formation and self–development [1 - 26]. In its structural and content units, the concepts and models of such pedagogically determined processes as "culture of independent work of the individual", "productive self-realization of the individual", "productive development of personality", "independent work of students", "scientific and pedagogical research of a student-teacher", "pedagogical conditions" are defined and will be considered by us. "pedagogical conditions for the inclusion of a future teacher in research work."

Let's define the conceptual framework of our research, identify criteria and indicators for the quality study of the inclusion of a future teacher in research work, formulate pedagogical conditions for the inclusion of a future teacher in research work.

The culture of independent work of the individual is a product of continuous professional education, visualized in the results, products and resources of self-development and self-realization of the individual, determined in the model of setting and solving the problem of personality development and the production, dissemination and modification of pedagogical tools and objects of culture, science, art, sports, etc. directions of anthropological conditioned models of socialization and self-realization of the individual, systematically ensuring the preservation of society and the uniqueness of the developing personality and its products of vital activity.

The culture of independent work of a personality is the process of timely creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions for the qualitative inclusion of a developing personality of a student or a subject of professional activity in a system of continuing professional education that determines the possibilities of personal development, the quality of self–improvement and self-realization, determined and measured in accordance with the specifics of the normal distribution of abilities and health, the requirements of socio-professional and educational relations,

the conditions of multi-media and multicultural norms and the possibilities of scientific and technological progress in solving the tasks of facilitating personal development, productive self-expression and self-realization, socially and professionally verified and adjusted in the model of development of education and socio-professional institutions.

Productive self–realization of a personality is the process of optimized determination of personally, socially and professionally significant and feasible prospects for the creation of goods and values, products of self-expression and self-affirmation within the framework of a deterministic problem of personality development included in the system and conditions of continuing professional education, regulating the quality of solving tasks and resources of personality development in the "lifelong education" model.

Productive personality development is the process of optimal formulation and resolution of contradictions of multi–media and multicultural relations that determine the physical, moral, and intellectual improvement of personality qualities and properties determined through intrapersonal changes that determine the quality of creating products of leading activities and communication, hobbies and leisure.

Independent work of students is a form of organization of pedagogical interaction and personal development of a student, determined by the standard of professional education and evaluated in the model of a particular training and profile of modern professional education, regulating the quality of competence formation and the ability of a person to productively, flexibly and timely solve problems of development and self-development, self-affirmation and self-realization, interaction and communication.

The scientific and pedagogical research of the student teacher is one of the directions of scientific research, the specifics of which is reduced to the formulation of the problem of research and solution at a certain level of quality, where the object and subject of research are directly related to the pedagogical processes implemented in the personal practice of the future teacher or the education system, which determines the possibility of productive formation of the personality of the future teacher through the products of his (her) scientific and pedagogical delights and innovations.

Pedagogical conditions are a set of optimally selected and implemented ideas and models of the organization of a pedagogically deterministic and verifiable process, built in accordance with the capabilities of the student and teacher's personality, the system of requirements and norms of modern continuing education and professional activity, the quality and nuances of the implementation of ideas and practices of taking into account the normal distribution of abilities and health in the model of health conservation and humanism.

The pedagogical conditions for the inclusion of a future teacher in research work are a set of optimally identified limitations and opportunities for building research work with future teachers studying in the system of secondary and higher professional pedagogical education, implementing the ideas and practice of humanism and productivity in development personality as a value and product of modern culture and education, which determines, in the range of its needs, the formulation and verification of the quality of a holistic understanding of the problem of preserving and multiplying the heritage of the anthropological environment and the noosphere as a whole.

Let's highlight the criteria and quality indicators for the inclusion of a future teacher in research work:

– the criteria for the quality of the future teacher's inclusion in research work will be three determinable and realizable areas or types of activity (self-realization of personality):

- 1) personal,
- 2) Social,
- 3) professional (professional and pedagogical);

– indicators of the quality of the future teacher's inclusion in research work:

a) the culture of independent work of the individual (teacher and student):

1) high level of culture formation independent work of a person, defined through the ability to independently identify and solve contradictions and tasks in the structure of leading activities and communication, hobbies and leisure, recreation and recovery of the body after a certain class and type of loads;

2) the average level of formation of the culture of independent work of the individual, determined through the easily guided and corrected ability of the personality of the future teacher to solve and clarify professional pedagogical and educational tasks;

3) the acceptable level of formation of a culture of independent work of a personality, determined through the products of self-development and self-realization of the personality of a teacher, the quality of which satisfies the socio-educational norms and practice of solving problems of professional pedagogical activity (we highlight the above levels the low level of formation of the culture of independent work of the individual, the specifics and possibilities of products and resources of self-realization of the teacher and the student, which does not meet the needs of the individual and society in solving the problems of development and multiplication of wealth and diversity of forms, methods, conditions of personal development in the model of leading activity and communication);

b) the Hirsch index of a student teacher and a teacher organizing classes in pedagogy;

c) the number of scientific and pedagogical publications and the quality of teaching practice.

The means of pedagogical measurements in the study include professional pedagogical cases of teachers, products of cooperation and co-creation, self-realization and self-affirmation of the personality of the future teacher. Let's formulate the pedagogical conditions for the qualitative inclusion of a future teacher in research work.

1. The readiness of the socio-educational space for a multidimensional, multicultural formulation and verification of the quality of solving problems of personal development in the model of leading activity and continuing professional education.

2. Creation of accessible, high-quality innovative software and pedagogical support for the study of modern pedagogy courses, the structure of which is the formation of the need for a culture of independent work of the individual and the proper level of provision with traditional and new information resources for the study of pedagogical disciplines. In the structure of each studied course of modern pedagogy, there should be tasks that determine the possibility of productive formation of a future teacher within the framework of the studied pedagogical discipline and reflect three directions/types assessment of the quality of the implemented activities directly related to the selected evaluation criteria:

1) personal

2) social

3) professional (professional and pedagogical).

3. Preparation of teachers in the system of continuing professional education for the possibility of solving problems of personal development and improving the quality of modern education by various types and forms of education that determine the capabilities of a student's personality in the context of his level of development and taking into account the model of normal distribution of abilities and health in the general sample – a set of students included in the holistic pedagogical process of continuing professional education.

4. Formation of the need for a healthy lifestyle life and a decent level of coexistence and development, determined and implemented in the model of modern labor law and continuing professional education.

5. Introduction of new models, refinement and optimization of traditional models for stimulating the quality work of teachers and the implementation of conditions for updating the software and pedagogical support of the courses taught.

6. Creating conditions for positive self-expression of the student's personality through the products of his socialization and self-realization in various competitions and programs that stimulate the activity and independence of the individual in choosing priorities for development and self-affirmation through socially and professionally demanded products of various areas of

anthropologically conditioned resources for the development of personality and society - science, culture, art, sports, etc. Organized scientific and practical conferences of students and students can be attributed to this direction.

7. Determining the future teacher's need for optimization of the possibilities of pedagogical reflection and situational clarification of the acme of the trajectory of professional pedagogical formation.

8. Dissemination of the relentlessly replenished and optimally modified experience of socialization and self-realization of the personality of the student and teacher within the framework of programs for the development of continuing professional education, stimulating qualitative transformations of socio-professional experience and products of the life of the individual and the team.

9. Optimization of the reserves of the functioning of educational and socialization institutions in solving the tasks of state policy in the field of education and the provision of educational services.

In this understanding, it is necessary to clarify in detail the possibilities of productive study of each studied course of modern pedagogy in the structure of teacher training in the direction "Pedagogical education" of various profiles training in the model of determining the quality of education of a graduate of a bachelor's degree teacher. To do this, it is necessary to clarify the software and pedagogical support for modern pedagogy courses, to conduct a statistical analysis of the results obtained in the training of future teachers in the model of learning and the formation of a culture of independent work of the individual using the technology of system-pedagogical modeling, facilitating the formulation and solution of tasks of personal development and productive self-affirmation and self-realization in the model of leading activity.

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